

METHOD OF ORGANIZING CIRCULAR CLASSES IN PRIMARY EDUCATION BASED ON THE STEAM APPROACH

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<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.13386800>

Abstract. *In the state educational standard, currently introduced in secondary schools, the main task is to develop students' life skills through technology lessons, problem-solving skills that graduates encounter in non-standard conditions, as well as the formation of basic competencies and worldviews necessary in independent life. This article presents considerations about the benefits of the Steam educational approach when conducting additional group classes in secondary schools.*

Keywords: *education, school, methodology, steam approach, abilities, competencies.*

Introduction. At present time the strategic goals of education require updating the content of education based on an analysis of its quality and compliance with international requirements for personnel training. The fact that information and communication technologies have radically changed society over the past 30 years encourages developed countries to pay more attention to the fight against external threats in their economic doctrines, and developing countries - to the fight against internal threats. In this sense, one of the most important factors in the sustainable transition of our republic to the stages of development is the rise of the education system in comprehensive schools to a new level. A new wave of technological changes is expected in the industry, which will enhance the role of innovation in the development of all sectors of the economy and reduce the influence of many traditional growth factors. One of such approaches is the ongoing work on the use of STEM in the educational process and its development. The transition to STEM education is rapidly organized in advanced countries of the world. The need to transition to STEM education for the training of specialists was first put forward in the United States by the National Research Council (NRC) and the National Science Foundation (NSF) and to carry out reforms in the education system, and STEM emphasized the importance of the transition to education [14]. Until 2020, in the education system of our country, when teaching natural sciences (the world around us, natural science), primary school students used the means of observation and experience in studying various natural phenomena. It is evident that teaching students to independently master materials related to pedagogical science, developing their educational and research activities through experience, small studies, project work is one of the important areas of education.

Analysis of literature on the topic. Currently, teaching of the Natural Sciences block is aimed at developing students' natural science, technical, environmental and economic literacy and developing critical and creative thinking - it creates the basis for the emergence of a scientific landscape. [9] Also, through this subject, interdisciplinary integration allows students to understand the possibilities and problems of modern scientific and technological development, understand the essence of environmental problems through the goals of sustainable development, ways of rational use of nature, principles of following a healthy lifestyle, and in everyday life aimed at developing the skills of using the acquired knowledge. From the recommendations of the legislation on the formation of natural science skills in primary school students, conducting

practical work on the topics "I am a researcher", on natural sciences [8] and on combining mathematics, art and technology, small project classes can be taken as a methodological basis [3]. The methodology of teaching natural science knowledge to primary school students based on a competency-based approach was studied by F.I. Ochilov [7], the issues of developing their research skills were studied on the basis of designing the educational process [5]. There are also methodological approaches by N. Turdiev, Zh. Osarowa [10] regarding the use of heuristic-productive educational technologies in developing logical skills of schoolchildren. Based on the analysis, we can conclude that it is possible to find an effective solution to the problem of interest in science and preparation for life activities based on developing the ability of positive thinking in primary school students. After all, as Mahatma Gandhi said: "Man is a product of thought, he becomes what he thinks."

Research methodology. Logical thinking of primary school teachers, a critical approach to the essence of the problem, a creative approach of students to the tasks directly and indirectly affect the effectiveness of learning. This task was approved by the Decree of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan PD-3931 dated September 5, 2018 "On measures to introduce new management principles in the public education system of Uzbekistan for 2018-2021". The program of measures to further improve the public education system of the republic "in section 2, paragraph 11: Improving the new state educational standards and curricula of general secondary education and at the same time STEM methods (science, technology, engineering and mathematics) to be implemented in practice step by step [1], according to the decision of the Minister of Public Education dated August 27, 2021 "The introduction of the STEM education system in comprehensive schools" the solution is to organize group classes for primary school students and organize lessons based on STEM approach on the basis of modern methods and an integrated approach. At the same time, this makes the issue of developing in today's students of comprehensive schools the necessary skills for studying, living and working in an industrially developed country relevant.

First of all, educators, methodologists, teachers, students and their parents, who are subjects of education, should know the information about the STEM approach and international research conducted in the direction of education quality, and apply them in practice. It is necessary to create opportunities for application. In particular, in the context of expected new technological changes in production, the use of the STEM approach in secondary comprehensive schools contributes to the development of creative and work skills of students, at the stage of post-school education or at the beginning of independent activity, serves as the main solution in the formation of the necessary basic competencies and worldviews. Today's educational trend is teaching subjects not in separate areas, but in a comprehensive manner, showing their general connection. In this regard, it is aimed at identifying the interests of students from school age and developing their talent and creativity, as well as educating scientifically inquisitive and creative personnel through the introduction of innovations. Another plus is that STEM inspires students explore the possibilities of inventors and scientists, explore the possibilities of technology, design like engineers, create like artists, think like mathematicians and of course, kids have fun playing.

Analysis and results. Club activities, which are one of the types of extracurricular activities in the proper organization of students' free time, are of great importance in the life of the further development of students' creative abilities. The child's ability to think freely during classes and publicly demonstrating his creative abilities increases his self-confidence. Also, during

training, along with teaching, children exchange creative experiences and this gives them the opportunity to increase their initiative. The club is a voluntary association of students interested in a certain field of knowledge and willing to engage in practical activities, and the diversity of programs and innovations in their content create new opportunities for the development of students as individuals.

Students will work on the topic "Unique Nature of Uzbekistan" in groups based on STEM approach.

Group 1: Science (natural sciences)

Participants in this group will ask: "Do you know me?" through a didactic game, a map of Uzbekistan is cut out in a separate form by region, and students in the group tell information about each region of Uzbekistan and place them in their place on the map.

Group 2: T (Technology)

The participants of this group will discuss what innovative technologies can be used to save water. Currently, there are problems such as what we can do to save water and what technology could solve this problem. It is appropriate to give students a project work. They will take a questionnaire from the group members and other students to find out the daily water consumption and analyze it. Based on the results of the survey, the action "I am the most thrifty student" will be announced. Thanks to this action, the students develop the virtue of thrift, and also benefit our ecology. This group can also be given a situation. Students think about how to solve environmental problems with the help of technology and look for solutions.

Group 3: Electronic Engineering

The participants of this group will be given the task of how to build a children's camp in the bosom of nature without harming the environment. Children make a model of the camp and can offer their project work on nature conservation.

Group 4: A(Art)

The participants of this group will draw images that reflect the nature of our country. The favorite activity of students is drawing. The participants of the group also present information based on the image of our country. For example, the names of the rivers they describe, the regions through which they flow or the names of the mountains and in which part of our country they are located, etc.

Group 5: (Mathematics)

Students of this group will get an idea of the nature of Uzbekistan based on mathematical data. For example, Uzbekistan borders 5 countries, there are 12 regions in our country, the length and width of our largest rivers are Amu Darya and Syr Darya.

By summarizing it should be concluded in lessons organized on the basis of STEM approach, students think and work together, interdisciplinary integration occurs, and the most interesting things are done in practice.

Conclusions and suggestions. Thus, instead of a conclusion, it can be emphasized that as a result of classes conducted on the basis of STEM approach in the educational process, students master practical research, learn to apply the acquired knowledge in real life situations in which independent work is carried out. The ability to act, teamwork, a friendly attitude is formed, which helps them study facts and acquire deep knowledge. Also, according to various studies and forecast trends, the demand for professions related to STEM sciences is an important stage in the

development of the scientific and technological profession of young people, solving the problems they face in their lives, and determining the future educational trajectory serves.

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